

Online appendix

Inequalities in diarrhea, pneumonia, and measles deaths, estimates from 21 sub-Saharan African countries

by

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1. Technical details of the optimization model implemented

We detail here the optimization methods applied in our modeling using the Demographic and Health Surveys. We draw and reproduce many of these details from the publication by Bolongaita and colleagues (2022) [1].

First, we begin with a population P , the diseases D_1 , D_2 , and D_3 (diarrhea, measles, or pneumonia), and a collection of risk factors RF_1, \dots, RF_n (for example, stunting, wasting, etc.). For each risk factor RF_j , we associate a limited number of possible instances per individual. For example, there are three possibilities associated with stunting: not stunted, stunted, or severely stunted, denoted by 1, 2, or 3, respectively.

Then, for each disease D_i with risk factor $RF_{i,j}$ (denoting risk factor j for disease i) and each individual's possibility α within $RF_{i,j}$, there is an associated relative risk $RR_{i,j,\alpha}$. This relative risk represents the relative risk associated with morbidity from D_i or with mortality from D_i .

Since we consider n risk factors, each individual from population P is assigned an n -dimensional risk factor profile, that is a list of n numbers. For example, if we consider stunting, underweight, and wasting, the 3-dimensional profile $\{1; 1; 1\}$ would represent an individual neither stunted, nor underweight, nor wasted; and the 3-dimensional profile $\{2; 3; 1\}$ would represent an individual stunted, severely underweight, and not wasted.

Second, for each risk factor profile RFP_k , let P_{RFP_k} be the number of individuals population P with that risk factor profile. Similarly, let ϕ_{i,RFP_k} be a number between 0 and 1 which captures the probability that an individual in P_{RFP_k} gets sick or dies from disease D_i .

We want to compare the multidimensional risk factor profiles to relative risks that each apply to one risk factor only. We introduce $RFP_{[x_j=\alpha]}$, which represents all the risk factor profiles whose risk factor j (= stunting, underweight, or wasting) is α . So, adapting the example above, $RFP_{[x_1=3]}$ would describe all possible 3-dimensional risk factor profiles of severely stunted individuals.

Third, to each disease D_i and risk factor RF_j we assign the quantity $\beta_{i,j}$, which captures the probability that an individual unaffected by risk factor RF_j gets sick or dies from disease D_i .

Subsequently, the application of the definition of relative risk furnishes 3 systems of equations, all linear in ϕ_{i,RFP_k} , one for each disease D_i ($i \in [1; 3]$; either diarrhea, measles or pneumonia):

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{RFP_k \in RFP_{[x_j=\alpha]}} P_{RFP_k} \phi_{1,RFP_k} &= \beta_{1,j} RR_{1,j,\alpha} \sum_{RFP_k \in RFP_{[x_j=\alpha]}} P_{RFP_k} \ , \\
\sum_{RFP_k \in RFP_{[x_j=\alpha]}} P_{RFP_k} \phi_{2,RFP_k} &= \beta_{2,j} RR_{2,j,\alpha} \sum_{RFP_k \in RFP_{[x_j=\alpha]}} P_{RFP_k} \ , \\
\sum_{RFP_k \in RFP_{[x_j=\alpha]}} P_{RFP_k} \phi_{3,RFP_k} &= \beta_{3,j} RR_{3,j,\alpha} \sum_{RFP_k \in RFP_{[x_j=\alpha]}} P_{RFP_k} \ .
\end{aligned}
\tag{1}$$

Fourth, we now need to solve the system of linear equations (1) for ϕ_i ($i \in [1; 3]$). In general, no solution will exist (as there are more unknowns than equations). Thus, our optimization task is to minimize $[\sum_{RFP_k \in RFP[x_j=\alpha]} [P_{RFP_k} * \phi_{i,RFP_k} - \beta_{i,j} * RR_{i,j,\alpha} * P_{RFP_k}]^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for $i = 1, 2, \text{ or } 3$. In doing that, we constrain the minimization of this objective function to the following probability region: $0 \leq \phi_{i,RFP_k} \leq 1$ and $\phi_{i,RFP_{x_l}} \leq \phi_{i,RFP_{x_m}}$ when $l < m$. As expressed above, these constraints guarantee that: firstly, ϕ_{i,RFP_k} corresponds to a probability; and, secondly, moving to a higher risk factor profile (say from l to m) does not decrease risk. These are the admissible combinations, as exposed in the Methods section (main text). Although this optimization approach will almost certainly not yield a unique set of minimizing probability solutions, it will still deliver a meaningful set of estimates for possible values of ϕ_i for each disease D_i .

Finally, the probability solutions constitute a probability distribution associated with population P . Each individual in P has a multidimensional risk factor profile RFP_k which can then be assigned the probability ϕ_{i,RFP_k} against disease D_i . This yields a probability distribution given by N independent events, where N is the size of population P and each event has a probability ϕ_{i,RFP_k} . Since each individual is also assigned a wealth quintile, this gives rise to probability distributions for each subpopulation of wealth quintiles. This is what allows us to estimate a distribution of cases and deaths for each disease D_i across wealth quintiles in a particular country.

2. List of all inputs and sources used in the optimization model

Some large parts of this section are reproduced from Bolongaita and colleagues (2022) [1].

2.1. Selection of risk and prognostic factors

Diarrhea – Rotavirus vaccine

Table S2 lists the relevant risk and prognostic factors for morbidity and mortality, respectively, reviewed for diarrhea, along with their relative risk magnitudes. Risk factors highlighted in grey were not included for various reasons described beneath the table.

Table S2. Relevant risk and prognostic factors for morbidity and mortality for diarrhea, along with their relative risk magnitudes and corresponding sources.

Morbidity risk factor	Relative risk (95% CI)	Source^a
Stunting	z-score < -3 SD: 1.9 (1.3-2.7) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.2 (1.1-1.5)	[3-7]
Underweight	z-score < -3 SD: 2.3 (2.1-2.8) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.2 (1.2-1.3)	[3,4,6,7]
Unsafe sanitation ^b	3.2 (2.9-3.5)	[4-6,8]
Wasting	z-score < -3 SD 105.8 (42.2-157.8) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 23.3 (9.0-35.8)	[3,4,6,7]
Having more than 2 children aged under 5 years ^c	1.7	[8]
Maternal literacy ^c	1.7	[5,8]
Mother's handwashing not practiced at critical time ^c	2.2	[5]
No handwashing with soap ^d	1.5 (1.4-1.6)	[4-6]
Non-exclusive breastfeeding ^d	None: 2.2 (1.5-3.2) Partial: 1.5 (1.0-2.3) Predominant: 1.2 (1.0-1.7) Discontinued: 1.3 (1.1-1.5)	[3,4,6,7]
Unsafe water source ^e	11.1 (4.3-22.9)	[4-6,8]
Vitamin A deficiency ^c	1.1 (1.0-1.3)	[3,4,6,7]
Zinc deficiency ^c	1.1 (1.1-1.2)	[3,4,6,7]
Mortality prognostic factor	Relative risk (95% CI)	Source^a
Stunting	z-score < -3 SD: 1.9 (1.3-2.7) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.2 (1.1-1.5)	[3-7]
Underweight	z-score < -3 SD: 2.3 (2.1-2.8) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.2 (1.2-1.3)	[3,4,6,7]
Wasting	1.5 (1.4-1.6)	[3,4,6,7]
No handwashing with soap ^d	z-score < -3 SD: 2.3 (2.1-2.8)	[4-6]
Non-exclusive breastfeeding ^d	None: 9.7 (2.4-28.1) Partial: 3.9 (1.5-8.3) Predominant: 2.1 1.0-4.6) Discontinued: 1.3 (1.1-1.5)	[3,4,6,7]
Vitamin A deficiency ^d	1.1 (1.0-1.3)	[3,4,6,7]
Zinc deficiency ^d	1.1 (1.1-1.2)	[3,4,6,7]

Table is adapted from Chang et al., 2018 [2].

CI confidence interval, SD standard deviation.

^aRisk and prognostic factors for rotavirus diarrhea were adapted from Chang et al., 2018 [2].

^bUnsafe sanitation was defined as a household not having access to a flush toilet (piped to sewer system, septic tank, or pit latrine), pit toilet latrine (ventilated or with slab), or composting toilet.

^cRisk factor not included in the analysis due to Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data unavailability.

^dRisk factor not included in the analysis due to lower relative risk.

^dRisk factor not included in the analysis due to poor data quality and/or poor variable definition.

^eRisk factor not included in the analysis due to computational limitations (using more than four risk factors for joint distribution analysis was considered computationally unfeasible).

Table S3 lists quintile-specific vaccination coverage and treatment-seeking behavior proportions used in the model. Data on immunization coverage (from the DHS) refer to the proportion of children who received the second rotavirus vaccination. Data on treatment-seeking behavior (from the DHS) refer to the proportion of children with diarrhea for whom treatment was sought from a health facility.

Table S3. Vaccination coverage and treatment-seeking behavior proportions used as model inputs for diarrhea.

Country	Quintile	Vaccination coverage	Treatment-seeking behavior
Angola	Poorest	0.178	0.347
	Poorer	0.236	0.416
	Middle	0.393	0.540
	Richer	0.500	0.391
	Richest	0.551	0.550
Burundi	Poorest	0.891	0.585
	Poorer	0.886	0.545
	Middle	0.923	0.613
	Richer	0.906	0.612
	Richest	0.891	0.638
Cameroon	Poorest	0.551	0.504
	Poorer	0.671	0.586
	Middle	0.735	0.603
	Richer	0.739	0.573
	Richest	0.836	0.517
Chad	Poorest	0	0.172
	Poorer	0	0.211
	Middle	0	0.262
	Richer	0	0.288
	Richest	0	0.377
Congo, Democratic Republic of	Poorest	0	0.372
	Poorer	0	0.445
	Middle	0	0.418
	Richer	0	0.384
	Richest	0	0.328
Ethiopia	Poorest	0.436	0.401
	Poorer	0.507	0.396
	Middle	0.530	0.435
	Richer	0.646	0.440
	Richest	0.786	0.606
Gambia	Poorest	0.963	0.628
	Poorer	0.952	0.613
	Middle	0.927	0.716
	Richer	0.933	0.599

	Richest	0.958	0.545
Ghana	Poorest	0.879	0.538
	Poorer	0.880	0.471
	Middle	0.894	0.336
	Richer	0.878	0.410
	Richest	0.907	0.455
Guinea	Poorest	0	0.478
	Poorer	0	0.637
	Middle	0	0.750
	Richer	0	0.759
	Richest	0	0.795
Kenya	Poorest	0	0.608
	Poorer	0	0.583
	Middle	0	0.564
	Richer	0	0.548
	Richest	0	0.556
Lesotho	Poorest	0	0.589
	Poorer	0	0.519
	Middle	0	0.431
	Richer	0	0.452
	Richest	0	0.546
Malawi	Poorest	0.885	0.662
	Poorer	0.916	0.633
	Middle	0.906	0.698
	Richer	0.939	0.688
	Richest	0.942	0.610
Mali	Poorest	0.607	0.477
	Poorer	0.709	0.453
	Middle	0.699	0.464
	Richer	0.743	0.495
	Richest	0.828	0.602
Namibia	Poorest	0	0.624
	Poorer	0	0.620
	Middle	0	0.648
	Richer	0	0.687
	Richest	0	0.613

Rwanda	Poorest	0.993	0.466
	Poorer	0.990	0.459
	Middle	0.996	0.542
	Richer	0.994	0.630
	Richest	0.992	0.550
Senegal	Poorest	0.881	0.454
	Poorer	0.969	0.429
	Middle	0.933	0.408
	Richer	0.978	0.501
	Richest	0.990	0.472
Sierra Leone	Poorest	0.835	0.793
	Poorer	0.852	0.733
	Middle	0.860	0.814
	Richer	0.881	0.718
	Richest	0.837	0.684
South Africa	Poorest	0.741	0.551
	Poorer	0.640	0.537
	Middle	0.704	0.803
	Richer	0.766	0.656
	Richest	0.650	0.778
Tanzania	Poorest	0.826	0.280
	Poorer	0.853	0.433
	Middle	0.901	0.448
	Richer	0.947	0.452
	Richest	0.968	0.531
Togo	Poorest	0	0.347
	Poorer	0	0.229
	Middle	0	0.230
	Richer	0	0.331
	Richest	0	0.401
Zambia	Poorest	0.885	0.735
	Poorer	0.905	0.746
	Middle	0.877	0.683
	Richer	0.943	0.618
	Richest	0.932	0.633
Zimbabwe	Poorest	0.457	0.347

	Poorer	0.488	0.401
	Middle	0.560	0.388
	Richer	0.479	0.381
	Richest	0.514	0.496

Measles – Measles-containing vaccine (MCV) vaccine

Table S4 lists the relevant risk and prognostic factors for morbidity and mortality reviewed for measles, along with their relative risk magnitudes. Risk factors highlighted in grey were not included for various reasons described beneath the table.

Table S4. Relevant risk and prognostic factors for morbidity and mortality for measles, along with their relative risk magnitudes and corresponding sources.

Morbidity risk factor	Relative risk (95% CI)	Source^a
Stunting	z-score < -3 SD: 2.5 (1.1-6.5) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.5 (1.0-3.2)	[3,4,6]
Underweight	z-score < -3 SD: 5.7 (1.8-12.4) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 2.5 (1.3-5.1)	[3,4,6]
Vitamin A deficiency ^b	1.4 (1.0-1.9)	[3,4,6,9]
Wasting	z-score < -3 SD: 37.9 (5.1-199.1) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 8.5 (1.3-42.8)	[3,4,6]
Having no other children vaccinated at home ^c	3.0	[9,10]
Maternal education ^c	3.2	[10]
Mortality prognostic factor	Relative risk (95% CI)	Source^a
Stunting	z-score < -3 SD: 2.5 (1.1-6.5) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.5 (1.0-3.2)	[3,4,6]
Underweight	z-score < -3 SD: 5.7 (1.8-12.4) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 2.5 (1.3-5.1)	[3,4]
Vitamin A deficiency ^b	1.4 (1.0-1.9)	[3,4,6,9]
Wasting	z-score < -3 SD: 37.9 (5.1-199.1) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 8.5 (1.3-42.8)	[3,4,6]
Age at infection ^{c,d}	NA	[9]
Infection with complication ^{c,d}	NA	[9]
Intensity of exposure and patterns of disease transmission ^{c,d}	NA	[9]
More than one child ^c	1.8	[9,10]
Overcrowding ^d	NA	[9,10]
Secondary (versus primary) exposure ^{c,d}	NA	[9]

CI confidence interval, SD standard deviation, NA not applicable.

^aRisk and prognostic factors for measles were adapted from Chang et al., 2018 [2].

^bVitamin A deficiency was defined as a child 6-59 months (about 5 years) of age who did not receive vitamin A supplements in the six months preceding the DHS interview.

^cRisk factor not included in the analysis due to Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data unavailability.

^dRisk factor not included in the analysis due to poor data quality and/or poor variable definition.

Table S5 lists quintile-specific immunization coverage and treatment-seeking behavior proportions. Data on immunization coverage (from the DHS) refer to the proportion of children

who received the first measles vaccination. Data on treatment-seeking behavior (from the DHS) refer to the average proportion of children with diarrhea or acute respiratory infection (ARI) for whom treatment was sought from a health facility.

Table S5. Vaccination coverage and treatment-seeking behavior proportions used as model inputs for measles.

Country	Quintile	Vaccination coverage	Treatment-seeking behavior
Angola	Poorest	0.317	0.252
	Poorer	0.426	0.454
	Middle	0.634	0.468
	Richer	0.719	0.664
	Richest	0.855	0.779
Burundi	Poorest	0.918	0.615
	Poorer	0.944	0.592
	Middle	0.947	0.584
	Richer	0.942	0.715
	Richest	0.938	0.673
Cameroon	Poorest	0.475	0.469
	Poorer	0.609	0.486
	Middle	0.650	0.547
	Richer	0.747	0.694
	Richest	0.863	0.714
Chad	Poorest	0.527	0.157
	Poorer	0.554	0.209
	Middle	0.581	0.235
	Richer	0.532	0.307
	Richest	0.674	0.443
Congo, Democratic Republic of	Poorest	0.618	0.372
	Poorer	0.673	0.399
	Middle	0.726	0.490
	Richer	0.752	0.392
	Richest	0.843	0.435
Ethiopia	Poorest	0.432	0.250
	Poorer	0.499	0.269
	Middle	0.544	0.289
	Richer	0.586	0.410
	Richest	0.743	0.402
Gambia	Poorest	0.940	0.668
	Poorer	0.922	0.757
	Middle	0.894	0.737
	Richer	0.882	0.571

	Richest	0.856	0.772
Ghana	Poorest	0.896	0.551
	Poorer	0.867	0.529
	Middle	0.906	0.616
	Richer	0.886	0.569
	Richest	0.945	0.540
Guinea	Poorest	0.273	0.740
	Poorer	0.316	0.729
	Middle	0.419	0.875
	Richer	0.430	0.891
	Richest	0.594	0.789
Kenya	Poorest	0.764	0.626
	Poorer	0.869	0.667
	Middle	0.883	0.649
	Richer	0.945	0.634
	Richest	0.931	0.735
Lesotho	Poorest	0.876	0.599
	Poorer	0.853	0.665
	Middle	0.971	0.634
	Richer	0.910	0.701
	Richest	0.897	0.532
Malawi	Poorest	0.900	0.778
	Poorer	0.924	0.767
	Middle	0.900	0.771
	Richer	0.913	0.791
	Richest	0.935	0.768
Mali	Poorest	0.602	0.743
	Poorer	0.684	0.583
	Middle	0.686	0.603
	Richer	0.719	0.779
	Richest	0.817	0.857
Namibia	Poorest	0.933	0.570
	Poorer	0.902	0.562
	Middle	0.889	0.656
	Richer	0.888	0.571
	Richest	0.852	0.568

Rwanda	Poorest	0.973	0.668
	Poorer	0.979	0.638
	Middle	0.969	0.623
	Richer	0.982	0.705
	Richest	0.987	0.774
Senegal	Poorest	0.757	0.543
	Poorer	0.883	0.364
	Middle	0.870	0.435
	Richer	0.902	0.729
	Richest	0.889	0.615
Sierra Leone	Poorest	0.738	0.838
	Poorer	0.755	0.826
	Middle	0.735	0.907
	Richer	0.736	0.841
	Richest	0.778	0.767
South Africa	Poorest	0.851	0.812
	Poorer	0.846	0.673
	Middle	0.875	0.686
	Richer	0.870	0.693
	Richest	0.876	0.733
Tanzania	Poorest	0.774	0.370
	Poorer	0.801	0.500
	Middle	0.886	0.495
	Richer	0.927	0.620
	Richest	0.943	0.784
Togo	Poorest	0.748	0.417
	Poorer	0.676	0.518
	Middle	0.675	0.399
	Richer	0.780	0.478
	Richest	0.834	0.691
Zambia	Poorest	0.885	0.694
	Poorer	0.910	0.797
	Middle	0.907	0.597
	Richer	0.905	0.754
	Richest	0.956	0.757
Zimbabwe	Poorest	0.765	0.432

	Poorer	0.762	0.430
	Middle	0.877	0.536
	Richer	0.845	0.547
	Richest	0.883	0.700

Pneumonia – Penta-3 (DTP-hepB-Hib) and pneumococcal conjugate vaccine (PCV)

Table S6 lists all the relevant risk factors for pneumonia, along with their relative risk magnitudes.

The risk factors highlighted in grey were not included for multiple reasons described underneath the table.

Table S6. List of the relevant risk factors for pneumonia, along with the extent of the relative risks and the corresponding sources.

Morbidity risk factor	Relative risk (95% CI)	Source^a
Underweight	z-score < -3 SD: 2.6 (1.9-4.4) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.4 (1.2-1.8)	[3,4,6,7]
Vitamin A deficiency ^b	1.6 (1.2-2.0)	[3,4,7,11]
Wasting	z-score < -3 SD: 47.7 (15.9-94.9) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 20.5 (7.1-37.9)	[3,4,6,7]
Crowding (more than 5 people per household) ^c	1.4	[11,12]
Exposed to household air pollution ^d	1.4	[4,11,12]
Low birth weight (< 2500g) ^d	1.4	[3,11,12]
Non-exclusive breastfeeding ^d	None: 4.5 (95% CI 1.0-18.3) Partial: 5.4 (95% CI 1.0-20.9) Predominant: 1.8 (95% CI 1.4-2.3)	[3,4,7,11]
Parental literacy level ^{d,e}	NA	[11,12]
Secondhand smoke ^d	1.2	[4,11,12]
Stunting ^e	z-score < -3 SD: 2.4 (1.1-5.1) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.3 (1.0-2.2)	[3,4,6]
Zinc deficiency ^d	1.8	[3,4,7,11]
Mortality prognostic factor	Relative risk (95% CI)	Source^a
Stunting	z-score < -3 SD: 2.4 (1.1-5.1) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.3 (1.0-2.2)	[3,4,6,7]
Underweight	z-score < -3 SD: 2.6 (1.9-4.4) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 1.4 (1.2-1.8)	[3,4,6,7]
Vitamin A deficiency ^b	1.6 (1.2-2.0)	[3,4,7,11]
Wasting	z-score < -3 SD: 47.7 (15.9-94.9) -2 SD < z-score < -3 SD: 20.5 (7.1-37.9)	[3,4,6,7]
Low birth weight (< 2500g) ^d	1.4	[3,11,12]
Non-exclusive breastfeeding ^d	None: 51.4 (95% CI 2.1-325.9) Partial: 2.8 (95% CI 1.3-5.2) Predominant: 1.9 (95% CI 1.0-4.1)	[3,4,7,11]
Secondhand smoke ^d	1.2	[4,11,12]
Zinc deficiency ^d	1.7	[3,4,7,11]

CI confidence interval, SD standard deviation.

^aRisk and prognostic factors for pneumonia were adapted from Chang et al., 2018 [2].

^bVitamin A deficiency was defined as a child 6-59 months (about 5 years) of age who did not receive vitamin A supplements in the six months preceding the DHS interview.

^cRisk factor not included in the analysis due to poor data quality and/or poor variable definition.

^dRisk factor not included in the analysis due to Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data unavailability.

^eRisk factor not included in the analysis due to lower relative risk.

Table S7 lists quintile-specific immunization coverage and treatment-seeking behavior proportions. Data on immunization coverage (from the DHS) refer to the proportion of children who received the third dose of pneumococcal vaccination (for pneumococcal pneumonia) and the third dose of DPT-HepB-Hib vaccine (for Hib pneumonia). Data on treatment-seeking behavior (from the DHS) refer to the proportion of children with ARI for whom treatment was sought from a health facility. If treatment-seeking behavior for ARI was unavailable, treatment seeking for fever was used.

Table S7. Vaccination coverage and treatment-seeking behavior proportions used as model inputs for pneumonia.

Country	Quintile	Vaccination coverage		Treatment-seeking behavior
		Pneumococcal	Hib	
Angola	Poorest	0.148	0.197	0.252
	Poorer	0.213	0.264	0.454
	Middle	0.329	0.427	0.468
	Richer	0.492	0.606	0.664
	Richest	0.570	0.622	0.779
Burundi	Poorest	0.934	0.961	0.615
	Poorer	0.940	0.971	0.592
	Middle	0.948	0.974	0.584
	Richer	0.928	0.964	0.715
	Richest	0.948	0.950	0.673
Cameroon	Poorest	0.527	0.529	0.469
	Poorer	0.654	0.681	0.611
	Middle	0.717	0.745	0.621
	Richer	0.753	0.804	0.694
	Richest	0.845	0.882	0.714
Chad	Poorest	0	0.272	0.157
	Poorer	0	0.324	0.209
	Middle	0	0.313	0.235
	Richer	0	0.332	0.307
	Richest	0	0.447	0.443
Congo, Democratic Republic of	Poorest	0	0.480	0.372
	Poorer	0	0.507	0.399
	Middle	0	0.565	0.490
	Richer	0	0.698	0.392
	Richest	0	0.830	0.435
Ethiopia	Poorest	0.360	0.364	0.250
	Poorer	0.489	0.504	0.269
	Middle	0.442	0.514	0.289
	Richer	0.560	0.632	0.410
	Richest	0.713	0.763	0.402
Gambia	Poorest	0.939	0.938	0.668
	Poorer	0.938	0.947	0.757
	Middle	0.911	0.912	0.737
	Richer	0.897	0.894	0.571
	Richest	0.929	0.947	0.772
Ghana	Poorest	0.584	0.830	0.551

	Poorer	0.526	0.887	0.529
	Middle	0.589	0.815	0.616
	Richer	0.674	0.858	0.569
	Richest	0.698	0.896	0.540
Guinea	Poorest	0	0.262	0.385
	Poorer	0	0.386	0.602
	Middle	0	0.385	0.657
	Richer	0	0.473	0.705
	Richest	0	0.546	0.789
Kenya	Poorest	0.789	0.833	0.626
	Poorer	0.842	0.901	0.667
	Middle	0.874	0.920	0.649
	Richer	0.883	0.937	0.634
	Richest	0.893	0.927	0.735
Lesotho	Poorest	0	0.837	0.615
	Poorer	0	0.809	0.592
	Middle	0	0.935	0.571
	Richer	0	0.880	0.701
	Richest	0	0.797	0.532
Malawi	Poorest	0.872	0.922	0.778
	Poorer	0.909	0.928	0.767
	Middle	0.887	0.938	0.771
	Richer	0.917	0.938	0.791
	Richest	0.879	0.925	0.768
Mali	Poorest	0.572	0.614	0.743
	Poorer	0.641	0.677	0.583
	Middle	0.697	0.711	0.603
	Richer	0.700	0.735	0.779
	Richest	0.793	0.815	0.857
Namibia	Poorest	0	0.869	0.570
	Poorer	0	0.829	0.562
	Middle	0	0.872	0.656
	Richer	0	0.861	0.571
	Richest	0	0.713	0.568
Rwanda	Poorest	0.978	0.985	0.523
	Poorer	0.984	0.984	0.565
	Middle	0.995	0.997	0.623
	Richer	0.994	0.994	0.705

	Richest	0.992	0.989	0.774
Senegal	Poorest	0.814	0.824	0.543
	Poorer	0.935	0.940	0.364
	Middle	0.917	0.919	0.435
	Richer	0.958	0.958	0.729
	Richest	0.975	0.986	0.615
Sierra Leone	Poorest	0.773	0.759	0.766
	Poorer	0.806	0.785	0.751
	Middle	0.779	0.784	0.760
	Richer	0.833	0.823	0.725
	Richest	0.783	0.758	0.767
South Africa	Poorest	0.682	0.720	0.640
	Poorer	0.545	0.548	0.673
	Middle	0.653	0.684	0.686
	Richer	0.611	0.678	0.693
	Richest	0.603	0.622	0.733
Tanzania	Poorest	0.751	0.803	0.370
	Poorer	0.848	0.874	0.500
	Middle	0.864	0.906	0.495
	Richer	0.923	0.937	0.620
	Richest	0.949	0.954	0.784
Togo	Poorest	0	0.840	0.417
	Poorer	0	0.777	0.518
	Middle	0	0.786	0.399
	Richer	0	0.831	0.478
	Richest	0	0.909	0.691
Zambia	Poorest	0.877	0.884	0.736
	Poorer	0.890	0.906	0.794
	Middle	0.888	0.930	0.842
	Richer	0.943	0.946	0.754
	Richest	0.904	0.960	0.757
Zimbabwe	Poorest	0.804	0.794	0.432
	Poorer	0.740	0.759	0.430
	Middle	0.888	0.915	0.536
	Richer	0.847	0.860	0.547
	Richest	0.843	0.869	0.700

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